

Development of a Web-Based Rainfall Forecasting System Using Long Short-Term Memory Networks

Abimbola H. Afolayan^{1*}, Joseph O. Oginni², and Kehinde O. Fasanya³

^{1, 2, 3} Department of Information Systems, Federal University of Technology, Akure, Nigeria

^{1*} Corresponding author: ahafolayan@futa.edu.ng; 08034121526

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Abstract

Nigeria has faced numerous challenges over time due to inadequate rainfall forecasting. This research aims to develop a predictive system for daily and monthly rainfall in Ondo State, using LSTM networks. The research uses a dataset from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) comprising daily rainfall records spanning 31 years (1992–2022). The LSTM model was developed and trained within the TensorFlow framework. Model performance was evaluated through Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and the Coefficient of Determination (R^2). The daily prediction model achieved an RMSE of 32, an MAE of 35, and an R^2 of 0.68, whereas the monthly prediction model recorded an RMSE of 7.4, an MAE of 6.6, and an R^2 of 0.92. The daily and monthly rainfall prediction models are deployed as an interactive web application using Streamlit, enabling users to select date ranges and view rainfall forecasts, which bridges the gap between advanced modelling and practical application for non-technical stakeholders.

Keywords: Rainfall Forecasting, Deep Learning, LSTM, Ondo State, Web Application.

INTRODUCTION

Rainfall prediction is vital in Nigeria, where agriculture and livelihoods depend on seasonal rainfall, and inaccurate forecasts can lead to crop failures, flooding, and poor water management challenges worsened by climate change (Adedeji *et al.*, 2018). Traditional forecasting methods, such as numerical weather prediction (NWP) and statistical models, often fall short because atmospheric systems are nonlinear and complex (Kagabo *et al.*, 2024). To address these limitations, techniques from computational intelligence, including soft computing and machine learning, have been investigated for their enhanced predictive abilities (Agboola *et al.*, 2012, 2013; Afolayan *et al.*, 2016; Hashni & Amudha, 2025).

Recent advances in deep learning have significantly improved climate modelling, especially for complex time-series data. Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks have proven effective at capturing long-range dependencies and nonlinear rainfall patterns, as reported by Kanchan & Shardoor (2021), Zhang *et al.* (2020), Nemade *et al.* (2023), and Wani *et al.* (2024). Ajah *et al.* (2025) compared LSTM and Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) models for daily rainfall prediction across Nigeria's six geopolitical zones, including Ondo State. The LSTM model achieved a notable MAE of 1.3470, an R^2 of 0.7501, an RMSE of 1.8021, and an accuracy of about 98%, confirming its reliability for rainfall forecasting. However, Ajah *et al.* (2025) and most similar studies remain mostly confined to academic research and have not been widely implemented on platforms accessible to non-technical users.

To address this limitation, our study develops a web-based rainfall prediction system driven by Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, using Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria, as a case study. Leveraging 31 years of ECMWF ERA5 daily rainfall data, the model achieves robust predictive performance and is deployed through an intuitive Streamlit interface. Unlike prior works that focus solely on model evaluation, this research translates deep learning into a practical, accessible platform, enabling end users without technical expertise to obtain localised, timely, and accurate rainfall forecasts. By integrating advanced neural architectures with interactive web technology, the system enhances climate resilience, supports agricultural planning, and informs disaster risk management, delivering both scientific and societal impact.

METHODOLOGY

This section describes the systematic process employed to develop the LSTM-based rainfall prediction model for Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria. Figure 1 shows the conceptual diagram of the system, highlighting major stages such as data collection and preprocessing, model design and architecture, and deployment, including the activities linked to each stage.

Figure 1. System Conceptual Diagram

Data Collection and Preprocessing

This study uses 31 years (1992–2022) of historical daily rainfall data for Ondo State, Nigeria, from the ECMWF ERA5 reanalysis dataset, comprising 11,323 records and six climate variables: pressure, dew point, precipitation, temperature, wind speed, and relative humidity.

Data preprocessing consisted of three main steps: cleaning, normalization, and dataset splitting. The dataset was complete, with no missing or duplicate values. Feature normalization was

performed using min-max scaling as shown in equation (1) to standardize variables between 0 and 1, improving training efficiency and numerical stability.

$$X_{scaled} = \frac{X - X_{min}}{X_{max} - X_{min}} \quad (1)$$

where X represents the original value, X_{min} denotes the minimum value from the original dataset, X_{max} indicates the maximum value in the original dataset, and X_{scaled} denotes the scaled value.

Finally, the research employs an 80:20 split, resulting in separate training and test sets. The training set comprises 9,058 samples, while the test set contains 2,265 samples.

Model Design and Architecture

LSTM networks, shown in Figure 2, are an enhanced version of Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) built to overcome the vanishing gradient problem during training (Hochreiter & Schmidhuber, 1997).

Figure 2. The LSTM Network Architecture.

LSTM networks use a unique gating mechanism to manage long-term dependencies in sequential data. The LSTM includes the cell state for memory retention, a forget gate to eliminate irrelevant information, an input gate to add new data, and an output gate to produce the final output. The cell state is updated using a tanh-activated candidate state, enabling the model to capture complex temporal patterns. Equations (2) – (7) provide a simplified representation of this process.

$$f_t = \sigma(W_f * [h_{t-1}, x_t]) \quad (2)$$

$$i_t = \sigma(W_i * [h_{t-1}, x_t]) \quad (3)$$

$$o_t = \sigma(W_o * [h_{t-1}, x_t]) \quad (4)$$

$$c'_t = \tanh(W_c * [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_c) \quad (5)$$

$$c_t = f_t * c_{t-1} + i_t * c'_t \quad (6)$$

$$h_t = o_t * \tanh(c_t) \quad (7)$$

where f_t , i_t , o_t , c'_t , c_t , and h_t denote the forget gate, input gate, output gate, candidate cell state, cell state update, and hidden state update, respectively. Additionally, σ represents the sigmoid activation function, while \tanh is the hyperbolic tangent activation function. W_f , W_i , W_o , and W_c denote the weight matrices, and b_c denotes the bias term for the candidate cell state. Furthermore, c_{t-1} indicates the cell state from the previous time step, and h_{t-1} and x_t refer to the previous hidden state and the current input, respectively.

Model Training and Evaluation Metrics

This research involved constructing an LSTM model in the TensorFlow framework, with key hyperparameters such as epochs, batch size, learning rate, and optimizer tuned experimentally for optimal performance. The tanh activation function was used in LSTM layers to capture nonlinear temporal patterns in rainfall data effectively. The Adam optimizer was selected due to its efficiency and adaptability. The model was trained for 100 epochs with a batch size of 64, balancing convergence speed and memory efficiency.

Model evaluation was conducted by minimizing the Mean Squared Error (MSE) during training, with performance tracked across epochs to monitor convergence and prevent overfitting. Following training, the model's performance was assessed on the test dataset using regression metrics such as RMSE, MAE, and R^2 to ensure a thorough evaluation of its predictive accuracy and robustness, as shown in equations (8) – (10).

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \quad (8)$$

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \quad (9)$$

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad (10)$$

where y_i is the actual rainfall value, \hat{y}_i is the predicted rainfall value, n is the number of observations, and \bar{y} is the mean of actual values.

Model Deployment

The final phase of the system focuses on deploying the trained LSTM model through a user-friendly web interface built with Streamlit. The model is serialized for efficient storage and reuse without retraining. Users can input specific dates to receive rainfall forecasts, which are presented visually through charts and graphs. On the backend, the Streamlit server retrieves precomputed predictions from a serialized CSV data layer, reducing computational load and improving system performance and scalability.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section outlines the findings of the LSTM rainfall prediction model for daily and monthly forecasts. The monthly model aggregates daily data to estimate total monthly precipitation. Figures 3 and 4 illustrate the performance of the LSTM model for monthly and daily rainfall forecasting. For monthly predictions (Figure 3), the model successfully captures seasonal rainfall dynamics, with clear peaks during the wet season and troughs in the dry season, and the overall trend aligns well with observed data. For daily forecasts (Figure 4), the model demonstrates strong predictive accuracy, closely following observed fluctuations. Occasional

overestimations during isolated heavy rainfall days suggest that short-term extremes remain challenging to predict precisely. Despite these minor deviations, the low MAE and RMSE values in Table 1 confirm the robustness of the LSTM approach for both temporal scales. The performance evaluation of the LSTM models shows that the daily rainfall forecast achieved moderate accuracy, with an MAE of 35, an RMSE of 32, and an R^2 of 0.68. In contrast, the monthly forecast model performed significantly better, with an MAE of 6.6, an RMSE of 7.4, and a high R^2 of 0.92.

Figure 3. Actual vs. predicted monthly rainfall for Akure

Figure 4. Actual vs. predicted daily rainfall for Akure

Table 1. Performance Evaluation

	MAE	RMSE	R^2
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Daily Forecast	35	32	0.68
Monthly Forecast	6.6	7.4	0.92

The trained LSTM model was deployed using Streamlit to create an interactive web interface that provides real-time rainfall forecasts. Users can input features or select dates to receive instant predictions through a forecasting dashboard. This dashboard features interactive plots that enable users to zoom in on specific timeframes, switch between daily and monthly forecasts, and download the visualizations for offline use (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. Rainfall Forecast Dashboard

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study developed a deep learning rainfall prediction model using LSTM networks tailored for Ondo State, Nigeria, trained on 31 years of daily climatic data from the ECMWF ERA5 dataset. The model showed strong predictive accuracy for both daily and monthly forecasts, achieving a daily MAE of 35, a daily RMSE of 32, and an R^2 of 0.68, as well as a monthly MAE of 6.6, a monthly RMSE of 7.4, and an R^2 of 0.92. By embedding the model into a user-friendly web interface using Streamlit, the research bridged the gap between sophisticated modelling and practical use for stakeholders. Future work intends to improve the model's responsiveness by adding real-time IoT and satellite data, as well as exploring advanced architectures like Bidirectional LSTMs, GRUs, and Transformers.

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